

Family Health Study and Presentation as a Comprehensive Teaching-Learning Method in Community Medicine for Medical Graduates

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ABSTRACT

Against growing need of more interactive learning tools to impart comprehensive knowledge and discussion based training to medical students, present study aimed to test efficacy of family health study presentations when incorporated in academic curriculum. A carefully chosen set of cross-sectional questionnaire was designed to get perception of participating students on the effectiveness, nature, advantages and future recommendation for including family health presentations in academics. Feedback is taken directly from undergraduate medical students as they are the true gainers from this learning tool. The feedback of participating students against questionnaire was clubbed in four categories of results namely improving the understanding of community medicine as a subject, acknowledging it as a non-burden interactive learning method, utility in skills enhancement and future prospects. There were five response options kept in the study – strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. Results of study as 75.5%, 65.92%, 72% and 80.7% responses were in favour of the positive aspects of family health presentation in the four categories of results. If neutral responses are also added to former positive responses – (19.26%, 9.62%, 20.7% and 12.5% respectively), overall non-negative response are 94.7%, 75.5%, 92.7% and 93.2% respectively. To conclude, results highlight that family health study presentations are meaningful activity and shows signs of being excellent learning methodology for medical coursework.

KEY WORDS: family health study, field visits, presentations, teaching-learning methods

INTRODUCTION:

The efficacy of traditional didactic lectures may not be very high as a method of teaching-learning. Didactic lectures often fail to transfer concepts and to enable deep understanding as effectively as active learning approaches. Innovative teaching-learning methods like studying a family and presenting the study to peers in the field can hold the attention span of the students for a longer time as there is higher level of participation for ensuring comprehensive learning and understanding. The authors believe that the method of family health study and presentations can contribute to achievement of the objectives of Competency Based Undergraduate Curriculum^[1].

This belief is also supported by the work of Bala A et al. ^[1] establishing equivalence of community

to ward and highlights that student's visit is meaningful if they are able to relate environmental, socio-economic and psychological factors with the family's health profile. Similarly, S.S. Kar et al. ^[2] conducted a study among 87 medical students at JIPMER, Puducherry. The student-centred learning (SCL) methodology was tested and most of the students had used PowerPoint presentation and videos for teaching. Students observed SCL as enjoyable, useful and informative technique.

Other relevant research works pertaining to family health study presentations include that of Mahajan PB^[3] who shared his experience at community medicine department in PIMS as coordinator for reorientation of medical education (ROME) wherein students worked in a community based research project, collected data and prepared research reports, study suggested enhanced presentation and public speaking skills through competition amongst themselves. Jaques D^[9] explained the choices available when teaching in groups like circular questioning, horseshoe groups, crossover groups, fishbowls and buzz group etc. Some choices require skilled and sensitive group handling

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within the group, while others need task setting and organising purposeful activities. Miller GE^[10] presented opinions for assessment of clinical skills/competence and performance, recommending need for graduates to develop the skill of acquiring information from various sources (human/ laboratory) and to analyse and interpret the data.

One of the problems faced by medical students is too much of information, too little time, too many students in crowded rooms, and examinations that discourage real learning as suggested by Rangachari (12). Thus it is quite fruitful to find and analyse various innovative learning tools available today, for imparting medical education to students in a way that ensures skills enhancement and retention of knowledge over longer time duration. Aim and objective of this study was to evaluate effectiveness of student seminars as a teaching-learning method in undergraduate medical programs in the Department of Community Medicine during the academic year 2018-19. A simple approach was used to obtain feedback from under-graduate students who have gone through this teaching-learning process and from the faculty of the department of Community Medicine who have implemented this. One of the core purposes of present study was to throw light at efficiency and effectiveness improvement via peer review when the findings of the study are shared with them through conference, seminars or presentations.

Objectives stated above are achieved better if a relevant topic of interactive discussion is provided to students. This is done through family health presentations as family is the fundamental institution of organization in society. Family visits give students exposure to understand association of various environmental factors, socio-economic factors and the psychological or emotional factors with holistic health status of the family.

During the family visits, students learn about family interactions and life cycle approach. However, it has been observed that due to some operational reasons, students do not benefit much from these family visits. The reasons mentioned by Bala A et al. (1) are that there is big gap of one year between family studies & final examination. Medical students do

family study practical in 2nd prof and appear for exam in new final year. When they are allocated families, they lag communication skills, clinical experience, or understanding of social science techniques or nutritional assessment skills. Keeping the above mentioned reasons in mind, the designed a trainingschedule for UG students that teaches them all these before they are sent to the field for undertaking the family studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a cross-sectional questionnaire-based study was conducted at PCMS & RC, Bhopal with participation of 2016 batch MBBS students. A questionnaire containing 10 direct questions of both open-ended and close-ended types was designed to obtain feedback from the participating undergraduate students, faculty and the postgraduate students who have conducted the programme. The data was compiled in presentable form for analysis through Microsoft excel.

Each undergraduate student was allotted a family in the community being served by the Rural or Urban Health Training Centres. This was done after a batch of about 35 students is taught in the class over a period of two weeks about how to conduct a family study. The student is given a format to be followed during the study. Then, each student visits the allotted family a few times by going to the village/ hamlet in the college bus along with his/her classmates. After the study, the student makes a Power Point (PPT) presentation (about 20 to 25 slides), by utilizing the support available from peers at Computer Centre of the college. Thereafter, each student delivers a power point presentation of his/her community based family study, in the presence of faculty members and post-graduate students of the department of community medicine. Each student gets about 20 minutes time for the presentation and discussion. This is an interactive session during which cross questions are being asked. The faculty, under-graduate students and post-graduate students hold discussions (both during and at the end of the presentation).

Study of a family as a cohesive unit that deals with the physical, mental, social and environmental

health of all its members is undertaken in this study. Studying an individual holistically in the natural environment of his family provides a student better understanding of patient's disease in its totality.

Students of 2016 MBBS batch at PCMS & RC, who have gone through the family study and presentations method in the Department of Community Medicine were included in the study. Students of the batch that were transferred to other medical college hospitals for their compulsory rotatory internship; and those who didn't give consent for participating in the study were excluded. This research intends to obtain feedback from students and faculty involved in this innovative teaching-learning method implemented in full scale for the 2016-batch of MBBS students; and share the results of study with peers of community medicine.

Feedback approach was kept at finding out if use of family health study presentation is comprehensive and if it includes the three domains of learning (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) and whether there is any positive impact on communication, inter-personal and soft skills enhancement of students. The methodology of identifying relevant questions revolved around following 3 domains - 1. Responses from Cognitive Domain: Whether this activity improved his/her understanding of the subject of Community Medicine?; 2. Response from Affective Domain: Whether this teaching-learning activity increased their interest in the subject?; 3. Response from Psycho-motor Domain: Whether this activity enhanced the power point presentation making/presentation skills? The idea of using above methodology was to assess whether subjected teaching methodology is a constructive, skill enhancing learning tool which prepares students for real life field interactions with common people and to analyse power of the tool in enhancing a student presentation skills and soft skills.

RESULTS:

There were five response options in the study – Strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. Results obtained in Table 1 and Table 2 suggest 75.5% and 65.92% participants believe that subjected learning tool enhances understanding

of community medicine and is not a burden, rather it is an interactive and interesting activity (Table 1 and Table 2). Amongst the participants, 72% (*Minimum of the seven questions mentioned here) and 80.7% responses were in favour of the positive aspects of family health presentation in the four category of results. Adding the neutral responses to former positive responses - 19.26%, 19.26%, 9.62%, 20.7% and 12.5% the overall non-negative response reaches to 94.7%, 75.5%, 92.7% and 93.2% respectively. The results are in agreement of family study & presentation activity being a promoter of comprehensive learning. The responding students believe this tool will be helpful in enhancing their presentation, soft, problem solving and time management skills and they recommended this activity to be part of upcoming MBBS course works in the discipline of community medicine.

Thus results match the partial requirements set up by MCI curriculum^[11] for UG courses that is focus on knowledge, skills enhancement, responsiveness and communication. Other improvement areas are also indirectly included in the result areas namely the observation, demonstration, assistance, analysis, critique, team leading, professionalism, integration, interpretation and collaboration.

The designed questionnaire included all possible kinds of response types which is evident from the fact that Figure 1 is a positive indicator while figure 2 is a negative indicator. Further, figure 3 is a neutral group of questions and at last figure 4 again indicates a positive response.

The total number of respondents were 135 (n= 135). When asked about their suggestions for improvement of the method, 27 did not respond. 108 participants provided their feedback. The suggestions given were requirement to improve transport facility, need for providing refreshments (snacks & drinks) during the field visits, reduction of time duration for which field visit in the village was arranged (3 hours) and the number of visits to the families be increased instead. Other suggestions are arrangement of equipment by RHTC/UHTC staff in the field (eg: BP apparatus, glucometer, etc.) and that the family visited must benefit from field visits through distribution of some medicines, pamphlets, etc.

DISCUSSION:

The respondents reported that the most common subjects during small group discussions

with families were nutrition and health, household environmental health, sanitation and hygiene, maternal and child health, family planning and

Table 1: Response to the question whether the T-L tool improved understanding of the subject.

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
This initiative has improved my understanding of community medicine	3 2.22%	4 2.96%	26 19.26%	64 47.407%	38 28.15%

Table 2: Response to perception of family health presentation activity as a burden.

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
This activity is more of a burden rather than being a part of academics	39 28.89%	50 37.04%	13 9.629%	17 12.59%	16 11.85%

Table 3: Response to the question if there is skill-enhancement through the discussed comprehensive and interactive learning tool.

Skills obtained by students through family study presentations	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	% Responses- Either Agree or Strongly Agree
Inculcating spirit of teamwork	3	4	10	74	44	87.4
Problem solving skill for helping families in distress	4	1	13	75	42	86.4
Presentation making skill	1	5	25	44	60	77
Public Speaking skill	4	3	17	63	48	82.2
Interpersonal communication skill	0	3	24	66	42	80
Communication and negotiation skills while interacting with classmates & faculty members	2	6	16	65	46	82.2
Time management skill	2	8	28	68	29	72

Table 4: Response to the question if students would recommend the T-L method to future MBBS batches

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
This practice needs to be continued for Upcoming batches of MBBS students.	4	5	17	44	65
%	2.96%	3.70%	12.59%	32.59%	48.15%

Figure 1: Response regarding improvement in understanding of community medicine subject.

Figure 2: Response to perception of activity as a burden rather than meaningful part of academics.

Figure 3: Response about Skills enhancement through this comprehensive and interactive teaching-learning tool.

Figure 4: Response to recommendation for future usage.

maternal and child health, family planning and immunization. The authors contend that this teaching-learning (T-L) method contributes by several means to the teaching of community medicine. This is not only teaching, but also training. In this initiative, each UG student witnesses presentation by all the 37 or 38 students of his group. They also contribute to the discussions and learn from the good practices and pitfalls of their group members. The PG students go through this exercise twice, for all the 150 students each year (once from urban area and once for rural area). This would happen for three consecutive years. Thus, it will prove to be a stupendous training. Also, the PG students guide the UG students and manage them during their preparation for the field work, during the visits to the community, during making of their reports and the preparation of power point presentations. This gives them tremendous opportunities to work as FGP (Friend, Guide and Philosopher) for UG students. They would get opportunities to apply the principles and methods of community medicine on a large number of families.

The new undergraduate curriculum is giving a lot of importance to building the right attitudes and ethics among the medical graduates and developing communication skills. It has developed a special module called 'Attitude, Ethics, and Communication (AETCOM)' which runs across different years of the MBBS course. Our T-L activity can contribute to achieving the objectives of AETCOM. Apart from being a good T-L activity, this gives some beneficial

side-effects for the institution in the following ways: This activity is bound to contribute to the society we serve. Students work as change agents for the community. This initiative thus improves the rapport of the department with the families in the community we serve. Also it creates the right impression and good will for the medical college in the community. Accounts get exposure to the real world when they visit the families in RHTC and UHTC areas of the medical college. The small group discussions in this teaching-learning method being studied were conducted after the students had visited the families during field visits. That is why 135 students could give a firm feedback that the method is comprehensive, involving the learning from all three domains. The feedback showed that their understanding of the community medicine subject improved (cognitive learning), their interest in the subject has increased (affective learning), and they obtained the much needed skills (psycho-motor learning). As this tool addressed the needs of all three domains of learning of community medicine students of MBBS, it is evident that this tool is comprehensive, interesting and more involving active learning tool.

Professional competence is an array of abilities across multiple domains or aspects of physician's performance in a certain context (Table 3). It is multi-dimensional, dynamic and changing over time, experience & setting as per Frank JR, Snell L et al (13). The authors believe that by fostering skills training and by increasing insight and commitment,

family study and presentation method enhances professional competence of the medical students.

CONCLUSION:

In contrast to traditional teaching through lectures, family presentation method seems to be more effective way of learning, which is relevant to self-development, is interactive and encompasses all the three domains of learning viacognitive, psychomotor and affective domains; thus making it a comprehensive learning method.

Family study and presentation activity ensures integrated learning participating students who went through the experience of field based family health study and presentations activity have overwhelmingly appreciated it as a worthwhile teaching learning method. They recommended it to be implemented during the coming academic years of MBBS.

Our study has analysed application of the programme on a single batch of students. It may be tried on more batches to know the affectivity and sustainability of this method on a continuous basis.

Field based Family studies conducted by UG students and presentations is an important teaching-learning method and hence needs to be incorporated on a regular basis in the medical curriculum.

The study obtained feed-back from the student participants about the teaching-learning method being evaluated, for its comprehensiveness. The feedback study statistically confirms that this teaching-learning method addresses all the three domains of learning; hence it is evident that the tool is comprehensive and the two components of communication, viz. inter-personal communication and public speaking skills of students are enhanced through proper implementation of this tool.

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